

Success Strategies in Digital Transformation: A Qualitative Research

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Abstract

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In recent years developing technology has led to changes in socio-economic structures in many areas. Businesses are also affected by the changes and try to adapt to new market conditions. Businesses have to transform their functions into digital in a holistic structure in order to perform their functions more agilely than their competitors with new business models. Based on this, this research aims to reveal the strategies that businesses implement in achieving a successful digital transformation. In line with the purpose of the research, the digital transformation success strategy of Enerjisa Üretim, which leads the sector with its products and services in the fields of energy production, energy supply, renewable energy and sustainability, is examined. The research data were obtained through document review and in-depth interviews with Enerjisa-Üretim information technologies digital business senior manager and expert employees. In this direction, a conceptual model was created by determining the strategies related to the digital transformation of the company, which is the subject of the research. In the research, it has been determined that strategies such as flexible and agile organizational structure, governance, digital leadership, digital capabilities, cooperation are adopted for the success of the digital transformation process. It is argued that digital transformation strategies can be successfully implemented in the focus of the organizational culture created. It has been observed that strategies for digital production are created with product lifecycle management and agile practices, based on the product. In addition, it can be said that Enerjisa Üretim has successfully determined and implemented digital transformation strategies.

Dijital Dönüşümde Başarı Stratejileri Üzerine Nitel Bir Araştırma

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Dijitalleşme,
Dijital Dönüşüm,
Dijital Stratejiler,
Enerjisa Üretim.

Son yıllarda gelişen teknoloji, pek çok alanda sosyo-ekonomik yapıları değişime sürüklemektedir. İşletmeler de söz konusu değişimden etkilenmekte ve yeni pazar şartlarına uyum sağlama çabasına girmektedir. İşletmeler, işlevlerini yeni iş modelleri ile rakiplerinden daha çevik biçimde yerine getirmek amacıyla bütünsel bir yapıda dijital dönüşüm zorundadır. Buradan hareketle bu araştırmada, işletmelerin başarılı bir dijital dönüşüm gerçekleştirmelerinde uyguladıkları stratejileri ortaya çıkarmak amaç edinmektedir. Araştırmanın amacı doğrultusunda enerji üretimi, enerji tedarigi, yenilenebilir enerji ve sürdürülebilirlik alanlarında ürün ve hizmetleriyle sektöre yön veren Enerjisa Üretim'in dijital dönüşüm başarı stratejisi incelenmektedir. Araştırma verileri, Enerjisa-Üretim bilgi teknolojileri dijital işletme üst düzey yöneticisi ve uzman çalışanlarıyla yapılan doküman incelemesi ve derinlemesine görüşmeler yoluyla elde edilmiştir. Araştırmada dijital dönüşüm sürecinin başarısı için esnek ve çevik organizasyon yapısı, yönetim, dijital liderlik, dijital yetenekler, iş birliği gibi stratejilerin benimsendiği tespit edilmiştir. Oluşturulan organizasyon kültürü odağında dijital dönüşüm stratejilerinin başarıyla uygulanabileceği görüşü savunulmaktadır. Dijital üretime ilişkin stratejilerin, ürünü temele alarak ürün yaşam döngüsü yönetimi ve çevik uygulamalarla oluşturulduğu gözlemlenmiştir. Ayrıca Enerjisa Üretim, dijital dönüşüm stratejilerini başarıyla belirleyerek uyguladığı söylenebilir.

INTRODUCTION

Innovations play a crucial role in the emergence of social, economic, and political changes around the world. In parallel with technological advancements from the past to the present, the societal structure is observed to be shaped accordingly. At the core of digital transformation lies Industry 4.0 technologies. New disruptive technologies are altering business structures and processes, pushing them towards a transformation process (Hitpass & Astudillo, 2019). This mandatory transformation stems from the innovation needs of businesses. Adapting to the changing market structure brings forth new competitive conditions, and the ability to turn transformation into an opportunity provides a competitive advantage between businesses (Porter & Millar, 1985). In this sense, innovations not only accelerate the pace of change for businesses but also reveal the efforts to possess resources for a successful transformation (Mert, 2019). Digitized systems in businesses offer innovations at every stage, from the supply process to production, marketing, and distribution processes. These developments in business systems and processes facilitate integration with the environment and society (Bhatnagar, 2017; Karaçuha & Pado, 2018). In the digital age, the inability to adapt to the requirements of societal change poses obstacles for significant future investments (Sambamurthy et al., 2003; Fukuyama, 2018). Firstly, the adoption of business strategies related to digitization is essential (Klein, 2020). In the subsequent step, being able to lead digital transformation and adapting the organization's capabilities to digital and implementing them is of paramount importance.

In the relevant literature, it is possible to encounter various studies addressing the digital transformation process of businesses. Kane, Palmer, Philips, Kiron & Buckley (2015) emphasize that digital transformation cannot be achieved with technology alone through their "*Strategy, Not Technology, Drives Digital Transformation*" model, stating the importance of leading transformation, developing capabilities, and creating culture. Schumacher, Erol & Sihn (2016) examine digital transformation in manufacturing businesses through their digitalization strategies model, focusing on dimensions such as "*Strategy*," "*Leadership*," "*Technology*," "*Governance*," "*Culture*," and "*Human Capital*." Similarly, Ismail, Khater & Zaki (2017) draw attention to the importance of digital transformation strategies and leadership in their "*Digital Transformation Content Strategy*" model. Canetta, Barni & Montini (2018) assess technology in a strategic vision in their "*Development of a Digitalization Maturity*" model, considering digital transformation as an integrated model that includes process, technology, strategy, and value-creating product. In addition to the aforementioned elements, Atak (2018) discusses digital awareness, adaptation, and collaboration. Klein (2020) also attempted to construct a conceptual model for businesses' digital transformations in a similar fashion. Oğan (2022), in research on Fortune 500 Turkey businesses; presents the mediation model of digital transformation culture in the relationship between digital transformation strategies and digital transformation performance. In the literature, models that highlight similar critical elements related to the digital transformation process in businesses are focused upon. In this context, within the framework of the relevant literature, a model related to the success of digital transformation strategies is tried to be revealed.

In today's world, as in every field, it is crucial for businesses to successfully carry out digital transformation. *Enerjisa Üretim Company* is an organization that leads the sector with its products and services in energy production, energy supply, renewable energy, and sustainability. By adopting its digital vision as a North Star, Enerjisa Üretim has taken on the mission of continuous development and renewal within its goals. The process of digital transformation in businesses is carried out under the leadership of the "*Information and Communication Technologies*" (IT) department, digital transformation office, or an equivalent unit. Therefore, in businesses, the digital transformation of IT group structures is primarily designed. Conceptual modeling of successful strategies for digital transformation in businesses is an important issue. Based on this, in this study, a conceptual model proposal is attempted to be developed for the successful implementation of digital transformation in businesses, with the example of Enerjisa Üretim. Especially since digital transformation has become a necessity for businesses, as in every field, it is expected that the conceptual modeling of the topic will

be guiding. Besides, since successful strategies in digital transformation are a new and emerging subject, it is believed that the relevant literature will benefit from this study.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Digital Transformation Process

As digitalization becomes widespread in many sectors such as energy, information, production, finance, food, and tourism, various models are being developed for digital transformation. Digital transformation represents an integrated process with other elements of the organization, starting with digital business strategies that are aware of the real need and continuing with digital applications integrated into business life (Oğan and Wolff, 2022). It can be seen that the digitalization process of Enerjisa Üretim is carried out in the framework of becoming compatible with innovations, being able to apply digital business models, and the digitalization of systems and processes. In this context, it can be said that the company's digitalization concept is designed with digital disruption, digital business, and digital transformation (Figure 1) (İnal, 2020a).

Figure 1. Digitalization Concept of Enerjisa Üretim

Digital Disruption: Technological innovations can reveal uncertainties in various areas of social life (Solzhenitsyn, 2000). The level of uncertainty created by new disruptive technologies in the environment is higher parallel to the magnitude of change, and it affects socio-economic areas. Digital technologies and uncertainties can be observed as consecutive processes, but digital disruptions can be prevented with high adaptation abilities to innovations or awareness of predictable changes. In other words, flexible organizational structures are more capable of coping with uncertainties (Basalla, 1998; Uys, 2002). It is expected that businesses that are sensitive to changes in the environment will focus on change with the necessary infrastructure. Because businesses that are prepared for change and do not allow uncertainties to arise gain an advantage (Ruelle, 1991). When looking at Enerjisa Üretim's digital transformation concept, there is awareness of the possible changes that may occur in the light of environmental developments. In other words, there is no digital disruption in the business ecosystem. Although there are environmental uncertainties, it is possible to minimize or eliminate the fuzziness depending on the company's flexibility level.

Digital Business: Another transformation concept of Enerjisa Üretim is designed as digital business. In the digital business stage, with the support of the technologies owned by organizations, work processes are moved to and carried out in digital environments (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). Digitized business processes accelerate enterprise systems and enable tasks to be performed quickly. With this feature, it can be said that the reflections of digital technologies on business life are quite deep and extensive (Schwab, 2017). Enerjisa Üretim, within the framework of its continuous improvement and process renewal goals, has prevented digital disruption and prepared the infrastructure for digital transformation through the EnerjisaAccess platform project. Thus, while the enterprise adopts a flexible structure, its adaptation to digital transformation is fast. In a

sense, digital business processes have been designed parallel to Enerjisa Üretim’s existing business platforms. EnerjisaAccess is not a critical application for Enerjisa Üretim. However, it can be said that it is the only application that is open to the outside due to the way the business in its industry is conducted (İnal, 2020a).

Digital Transformation: Digitalization means the digitization of all systems and processes in various fields with the support of information and communication technologies. Today, it is observed that network-based digital technologies added to information technologies make business systems and processes smarter (Yoo, 2010; Wang et al., 2010; Guo and Leu, 2013; Von Solms and Van Niekerk, 2013; Lee et al., 2014; Drath and Horch, 2014; Bahrin et al., 2016; Zawra et al., 2017; Fahem et al., 2018). However, having a digital technology infrastructure alone is not sufficient for digital transformation of businesses. To achieve this, technology needs to be combined with organizational structure and other organizational elements. It can be said that Enerjisa Üretim’s digital transformation efforts continue with a holistic design where digital capabilities exist in its systems and processes. For example, the Enerjisa Üretim CPS tool is one of the newly designed digital applications for production sharing/direction (dispatch in technical jargon) between power plants, and it sends tasks related to automation to related institutions for day-ahead and intraday planning and optimization purposes. Firstly, it is accepted that digital transformation is a process that can mature over time. In this context, the goals of continuous improvement and adaptation to emerging innovations will continue (İnal, 2020a).

Digital Transformation Strategies

The emergence of digital transformation is not likely to happen suddenly, and it is known that it can be successfully realized within a well-designed process that incorporates future predictions. The emergence of digitization as a necessity makes it necessary for businesses to determine their strategies within the framework of future predictions. To carry out their digital transformations, businesses must first embrace this process by adopting certain strategies that are based on business resources derived from digital technologies. Digital capabilities integrated with business resources reveal the organizational culture. No talent that is not focused on the culture of the organization can be expected to contribute to digital transformation. In order to successfully carry out digital transformation, Enerjisa Üretim develops a visionary perspective and realistic strategies. These strategies are expressed in general terms as governance, agility, digital leadership, digital capabilities, collaboration, and digital HRM (Figure 2) (İnal, 2020b).

Figure 2. Digital Transformation Strategies of Enerjisa Üretim

Digitalization advocates obtaining more information by searching for it. Therefore, the openness, accessibility, and transparent sharing of information are important in order to produce. Thus, governance, which is one of the basic principles of development through knowledge, is a digital transformation strategy for businesses. Agility is becoming the focus of general goals for businesses whose activities and decision-making mechanisms have

accelerated with digital technologies. In other words, it is considered an important strategy for digital transformation (Rigby, 2020). Leading the process is undoubtedly one of the critical elements for success. A leadership understanding with digital skills that believes in the necessity of digital transformation is a strong strategy for creating organizational culture. At the same time, human capital, new generation systems, and other digital skills that the company has are seen as critical strategies that provide organizational integrity with transformation. In the digital age, businesses focus more on digital skills, which can make access to them insufficient or difficult. To overcome this, it is an important strategic step to render the HRM process more agile. Collaborations with other businesses within the same ecosystem are also considered an important strategy because they offer the opportunity to benefit from their digital skills.

Digital Goals: Data analytics and cloud computing are important technologies that constitute the infrastructure of digital transformation. Big data refers to the data that can be obtained from all kinds of smart systems through network technologies (World Bank Group, 2017). As the use of smart systems increases, exponential data is being generated (Reinsel et al., 2017). Therefore, it should be considered as a valuable skill that can shed light on activities that can be predicted for the business vision. Cloud computing also serves the same purpose by storing information from big data in a certain systematic way. With cloud computing, it is possible to obtain data that can add value to the new production process (Zhang et al., 2012). The digital goals of Enerjisa Üretim's IT structure are focused on creating a flexible and agile organization built around the core digital technology capability. It is understood that strengthening data analysis in the IT structure is critical for digital transformation. This also creates an important digital capability for the business. It is believed that digital technologies that transform the IT structure into more flexible and agile processes contribute to the sustainability of the company (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Digital Goals of Enerjisa Üretim

The Success of Digital Transformation: The development of digital strategies by businesses with a digital vision is crucial for achieving their digital transformation goals. Taking a strategic approach to digital transformation requires processes integrated with an inclusive organizational culture. Focusing on the business vision and creating a harmonious organizational structure in line with internal and external environmental factors provides a competitive advantage (Nedelea & Paun, 2009).

Figure 4. Enerjisa Üretim Digital Transformation Success Factors

Leading digital transformation involves innovative and transformative abilities. As organizational structures are renewed in the digital age, they evolve into flexible, agile, and digital processes with new business models. Leadership skills are needed to integrate the organization with digital systems in each element. In Enerjisa Üretim, leadership is seen more as a mentoring role with the accumulated knowledge, experience, and guidance of the leader. Thus, it is expected that the mentoring leader will direct the followers towards the goal with awareness, knowledge, and belief about the subject. From this perspective, possessing leadership skills should also be considered a valuable organizational asset. Similarly, it is necessary for the company to have technological infrastructure resources that can help them reach their goals faster and partners they can collaborate with in fundamental abilities. Therefore, it seems possible to achieve transformation with an inclusive organizational culture that covers all aspects of the company (Figure 4).

Digital Information and Communication Technologies (IT)

The vision of digital transformation concentrates on creating value in the products and services of the company. Besides, it aims to optimize digital processes according to customer needs and expectations and to achieve change through a shared culture (Dahlström, Desmet & Singer, 2017). To create value in the products and services of the company, it is crucial to acquire and develop the necessary skills (Bughin, Deakin & O’Beirne, 2019).

Enerjisa Üretim is creating the North Star model with its digital IT, which is capable of producing digital products and at the same time has an external customer related to the product. In a sense, it can be said that the IT group continues its development by determining the digital as its North Star. As illustrated in Figure 5, production IT adopts an agile working model while focusing on digital products. Generic processes are designed through the digital infrastructure owned by production. Communication platforms and collaboration with business partners are maintained to increase coordination with internal customers. The life cycle of the product is a process that needs to be managed for the product to meet needs and continue its life. Therefore, continuous improvement or innovation efforts related to the product are monitored. A product management process is adopted where all responsibility for the product is carried out. For this, importance is given to the leadership of the product manager. Agile structures are created through digital applications used in product development, and quick experiences are revealed about the results. Thus, the “MVP” or “Minimum Viable Product” product model, which can respond to users’ needs in the simplest and shortest way, is offered.

Figure 5. Product Support Network – North Star Model

METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to identify some strategies that can guide businesses to successfully carry out their digital transformations. Since the research includes identifying, classifying, and describing the relationships between the elements of the business's digital transformation, it has qualitative research characteristics (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). The reliability and validity of scientific research is an important criterion. The reliability and validity of qualitative research mostly depend on the credibility of the researcher, having in-depth knowledge of the subject, and the accuracy of the research (Sandelowski, 1986; Başkale, 2016). Because qualitative research deals with a small sample group, so in-depth findings on the subject can be reached (Houser, 2015). In this context, the research is based on two phases: semi-structured in-depth interview and secondary data. First of all, articles, theses and models related to digitalization and digital transformation in the literature were searched. Within the framework of the digital transformation literature, 7 interview questions were structured. Afterwards, a model was tried to be created according to the answers given to the semi-structured interview questions. Document analysis is a systematic process that evaluates both electronic and print materials to examine primary and secondary data relevant to the research (Bowen, 2009; Özkan, 2021). To support and confirm the findings of document analysis, various techniques such as interviews and observations are utilized (Yin, 1994). In this direction, a meeting was held with the top management of the Enerjisa Üretim IT (Information and Communication Technologies) Digital Business and the employees unit to identify the strategies related to digital transformation.

In this research, the preference of a group was consulted in order to some success strategies in digital transformation. It was thought that it would be appropriate to focus on a business that can compete in the international market, which attracts attention with its digitalization activities in the energy field. Enerjisa Üretim has been operating in the energy sector since 1996. With a mission to constantly improve, the company has represented successful leadership in the energy sector in Turkey for many years with a responsible, transparent, and flexible management structure. The company continues to develop its products and services in energy production, energy supply, renewable energy, and sustainability. Moreover, Enerjisa Üretim operates with 5 different technologies, 23 power plants, a capacity of 3,727 MW, and 950 employees (Enerjisa Üretim, 2023).

Working group of the research was determined as Enerjisa Production IT and Digital Business Department. There are 82 employees in the said department. In this direction, purposive sampling, which is a nonprobabilistic sampling method, was used in the research and 1 senior manager and 10 expert employees were selected for the application. In the purposeful sampling method, an application is made to a consciously determined group in line with the purpose of the research (Denscombe, 2017). Different opinions are expressed

about determining the sample size in qualitative studies. For example, in case studies that try to reveal a process, it is stated that there can be more than one person who has a relationship with at most 4 or 5 situations (Creswell, 2017). According to another view, in qualitative research, since data repetition starts after a certain time, theoretical saturation can be achieved with less number of participants (Baltacı, 2019). For this reason, a total of 11 employees reflecting the organizational climate were consulted for the research data. After several mutual information-sharing meetings, seven questions were identified and data was obtained through a semi-structured interview technique. The questions in the semi-structured interview form are as follows:

- Why is digital transformation necessary for your company?
- What are your company's digital transformation strategies?
- How is your company leading the digital transformation?
- How do you evaluate the role of human resources and culture in realizing your company's digital transformation strategies?
- How do you evaluate the role of human resources and culture in realizing your company's digital transformation strategies?
- What factors determine the success of digital transformation?
- Do you evaluate the performance of your company's digital transformation?
- What are the obstacles to digital transformation for your company?

In regards to the interview questions, ethical committee approval was obtained from Artvin Coruh University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee on 03.29.2023 with the approval number of E-18457941-050.99-87467. The research data was collected through document analysis and an interview in April 2023. In analyzing the research data, first, the data obtained through document analysis was presented as a conceptual model proposal. Lastly, in the analysis stage of the data obtained through the semi-structured interview form technique, abbreviations were made in the manager's responses, and the main focus was determined to identify the company's digital transformation strategies. Within this scope, the obtained data from the managerial perspective were subjected to content analysis and presented as the findings of the research.

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

The semi-structured interview form included questions about the necessity of digital transformation for businesses, digital transformation strategies, leading digital transformation, the role of human resources and culture in digital transformation, success factors in digital transformation, and digital transformation performance. The responses of the manager and employees to these questions are presented and interpreted in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 below.

Table 1. Findings Pertaining to the Necessity of Transformation

Why is digital transformation necessary for your company?	<p><i>The realization of digital transformation is an important strategy for Enerjisa Üretim. In order to provide a competitive advantage to the business, digitalization and agility are adopted together. “Why would a power generation business want to be digital and agile?” When the question is evaluated, the outputs are formed under four main headings;</i></p> <p><i>(a) The concept of “digital” is a forward-growing competence to gain more insights from data and make the right decision at the right time.</i></p> <p><i>(b) Being prepared for this, considering the reality that the electricity generation sector has not yet experienced a “disruptive innovation” in its full sense.</i></p> <p><i>(c) The imperative to optimize our production methods for sustainability and environmental awareness.</i></p> <p><i>(d) The need for agile and value-oriented management principles to acquire and retain new talent.</i></p>
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The perspective of Enerjisa Üretim regarding why digital transformation is a necessity for companies is presented in Table 1. Firstly, digital transformation is adopted as a strategy for Enerjisa Üretim. With this statement, it can be claimed that Enerjisa Üretim is digitally aware of and concentrates on its capabilities through its digital vision. It is possible to assert that they perceive it as a need to maintain their competitive advantage in the market and sustain their functions.

Table 2. Findings Pertaining to the Digital Transformation Strategies

What are your company's digital transformation strategies?	<p><i>The main purpose of digital transformation is to improve and streamline the way central and field business units operate, as well as to prepare for upcoming disruptive changes. In addition, the goal is to create a prepared environment for constructive disruptions that are expected to occur. The adopted vision of the company, "to be an IT company that produces electricity," suggests that it is not acceptable for only the IT department to embrace the digitalization mission. Therefore, it is crucial for all business units to unite under a correct understanding of digitalization. Especially in sectors such as electricity generation where non-unique products are concerned, digitalization approaches that only affect the top line are insufficient. Thus, it is important to adopt a digitalization purpose that will affect the bottom line, while also serving growth, expansion, and scaling scenarios. Existing services must be able to grow more flexibly, and know-how exchange must be more efficiently facilitated. Supporting growth through traditional methods is difficult, costly, and slow. Therefore, it is expected that the digital perspective and expertise will be established in all business units.</i></p>
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Enerjisa Üretim's digital transformation strategies are presented in Table 2. Firstly, it can be claimed that Enerjisa Üretim adopts a strategy of being prepared for innovation and change, in other words, not facing digital disruption. It is also seen as an important strategy to adopt a predictable future vision for this purpose. It is understood that the business applies its digital transformation strategies in all business units and capabilities. Supporting business processes with technology, adopting a flexible organizational structure to easily adapt to innovations, and facilitating know-how exchange are among the other strategies.

Table 3. Findings Pertaining to Leading the Digital Transformation

How is your company leading the digital transformation?	<p><i>Enerjisa Üretim company holds a leading position in the market it operates in. Therefore, the companies it can compare itself with are on a global scale. The approach here is to focus on "next practices" rather than "best practices." The main aim is for the company, which is deprived of the developmental power of competition, to define its own cultural and digital development path. It is necessary for the departments within the company to write their own digital transformation stories with the catalytic and guiding support of IT. For the company to lead the industry, it is important for this logic to be collectively adopted and for IT to take the lead in making this logic established within the company. For this purpose, a "Digital Journey Mentorship" unit was established within the IT department and an IT Business Partner structure was established for each business unit. Each business unit has an assigned ITBP. The main task of these ITBPs is; to define "Digital Journey Roadmaps" of business units. These roadmaps are made separately for each business unit and each domain, and are planned as short-term, medium-term and long-term. These agreement texts, which were prepared together with the business units and then signed together, enable the business to see the front more clearly in the digital leadership concept. The main tasks of ITBPs are to follow digital developments in the energy sector, IT sector and other related environmental sectors, to analyze their compliance, to integrate business units and appropriate innovations into the digital journey maps of business units.</i></p>
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The information regarding the extent to which Enerjisa Üretim leads digital transformation is presented in Table 3. Under the leadership of Enerjisa Üretim IT group, the company adopts mentoring to processes and capabilities in its other units. It is seen that an activity aimed at raising digital awareness, which is an important priority for digital transformation, is included. Then, technology, applications, and capabilities are aligned. This also means leading the culture to be created. Enerjisa Üretim, while leading digital transformation within its own structure, also undertakes a leadership mission for other companies in the sector.

Table 4. Findings Pertaining to the Roles of Human Resources and Culture in the Digital Transformation

How do you evaluate the role of human resources and culture in realizing digital transformation strategies?	<p><i>Digital transformation is a cultural transformation rather than a technical transformation. Therefore, it is important to firstly adopt approaches, increase digital prowess for all employees, correctly understand the extent to which the status-quo cannot continue, how new approaches and upcoming constructive disruptions will affect the industry, business, business units and indirectly people. Accordingly, we accept People and Culture as the most important and constant part of digital transformation. We consider a culture change necessary not only for the IT unit but for the entire enterprise, and we maintain a culture change management within the framework of a planned program.</i></p>
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Information regarding the extent to which Enerjisa Üretim evaluates the role of human resources and culture in carrying out digital transformation is presented in Table 4. Enerjisa Üretim evaluates digital transformation within a common cultural framework that encompasses all organizational processes. Therefore, it attaches importance to the development of digital skills in systems and processes. It is aware that digital transformation essentially requires a cultural change and manages the process with this perspective. The human capital resource is the one that would create cultural change.

Table 5. Findings Pertaining to the Success Strategies of Digital Transformation

<p>On which factors does the success of digital transformation depend?</p>	<p><i>Upon evaluating the success of digital transformation, regardless of priority order, it can be claimed that it includes the following factors;</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>(a) Human and Cultural development and mental structure transformation</i> <i>(b) Agile approach and product-oriented designs</i> <i>(c) Business unit – IT integration and the digital prowess expected to come with it</i> <i>(d) Stakeholder management involving technology producing companies and suppliers</i> <i>(e) Follow industry status and trends (local and global) as part of the business</i> <i>(f) Design and maintain a systematic Digital Journey Map.</i> <p><i>The absence of any of these factors is the biggest obstacle to successful digital transformation. Changing the way of thinking is the largest part of digital transformation. It is only possible to talk about a real change in thinking and the digital transformation it brings in an environment where employees have changed their way of thinking, are questioning, not afraid of experimental methods, see no benefit from the top-down hierarchy, and work transparently.</i></p>
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Information on the factors that affect the success of digital transformation is presented in Table 5. It can be seen that Enerjisa Üretim identifies the factors that affect the success of digital transformation as digital skills, digital awareness, having/producing technology, collaboration, agile structures, and continuous renewal. It can be argued that all these factors are possible through the transformation of culture.

Table 6. Findings Pertaining to the Digital Transformation Performance

<p>Can you evaluate the digital transformation performance of your company?</p>	<p><i>The performance of digital transformation is evaluated by both internal and external sources. In order to avoid the possibility of bias in evaluations made by internal sources, more weight has been given to external evaluations. Accordingly, there are evaluations such as "Digital Execution Scorecard" by Gartner and "Digital Acceleration Index" by Boston Consulting Group. In both evaluation outputs, Enerjisa Üretim's position was found to be quite good compared to industry benchmarks. The evaluation outputs are reduced to improvement recommendations and actionable items. The recommended actions are integrated into the Digital Journey Maps through the relevant units and ITBPs. These studies with external analysts will be repeated within the recommended renewal process, and a status assessment will be conducted again.</i></p>
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Information on the company's digital transformation performance is presented in Table 6. It can be seen that Enerjisa Üretim utilizes different sources to evaluate its digital transformation activities. This also shows that the company obtains realistic results by giving importance to objective control mechanisms. As part of the evaluations, it compares itself with the international sector and provides improvements. In this direction, it can be said that it continues to take action for the transformation.

Table 7. Findings Pertaining to the Obstacles to Digital Transformation

<p>What are the obstacles to digital transformation for your company?</p>	<p><i>The main purpose of the transformation adventure, which started about three or four years ago; is to create the digital approach of the business, establish the culture and to accelerate this by creating a customized “digital transformation” approach for the company. In order to accelerate the digital transformation, emphasize its importance and do the authorization correctly (empowerment), the IT structure was raised to the level of a General Manager and the unit was enabled to work directly with the CEO. In addition, it has been ensured that it is directly integrated not only in IT, but also in business goal cards, long-term planning and strategies. Thanks to these actions, the digital transformation in the business has been opened directly. Due to what has already been done, ongoing investments and support, there is no obstacle in terms of politics, logistics and strategy. Although with a decreasing trend, our employees, who still have difficulty in adapting to the new approach by leaving their comfort zones, old ways of doing business and learned learnings, are seen as the most important obstacles which are also gradually removed.</i></p>
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The information regarding the obstacles facing digital transformation is presented in Table 7. It can be asserted that Enerjisa Üretim overcomes the barriers in compliance with its vision. The fact that their digital transformation strategies have been identified and their tendencies towards this direction eliminate the barriers. However, failure to adapt to innovative working models, falling behind in technological trends, prejudice, and most importantly, the inability to create a digital culture are perceived as significant obstacles.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the necessity of digital transformation as an important strategy for companies, this study has yielded significant results. In order to achieve a successful digital transformation, strategies have been identified, supported by an application in the IT structure of Enerjisa Üretim, which holds a leading position in the energy sector. According to the research findings, Enerjisa Üretim’s focal point in digital transformation is on possessing and developing technological skills. With its technical and managerial capabilities, it also assumes responsibility in other companies in the industry. Therefore, it emphasizes the necessity of always being prepared for change, since change is deemed necessary for transformation.

The digital transformation strategies of EnerjisaÜretim are determined in general areas; improving business models, creating flexible structures, developing agile capabilities, collaborating with stakeholders using core competencies, enhancing the company’s “know-how” value, and sustaining digital transformation as a culture. Good leadership skills for digital transformation are also adopted as an important strategy. In this context, a strong alliance is formed with the company’s internal resources, technology-producing companies, and the IT department. Thus, in the digital transformation process, EnerjisaÜretim sets a good example as a leader in the market.

The factors that affect the success of Enerjisa Üretim's digital transformation are having digital intelligence, being aware of digital transformation and moving in that direction, focusing on agile and product-oriented designs, having digital skills, creating collaborations with other business capabilities that can better showcase quality, focusing on continuous improvement, and being able to clearly define and implement strategies for this purpose. Executing digital transformation is a top priority strategy for Enerjisa Üretim. It is thought that the feasibility of this strategy depends on the maturity of the organizational culture. Therefore, it appears to be extremely critical for businesses to establish an organizational culture in order to successfully carry out digital transformation. Therefore, it is recommended that businesses develop their digital transformation strategies with

a focus on digital culture. Digital skills cannot be ignored in achieving successful transformation. Digital skills should be present in every resource that the business has in its systems and processes. Then, it is necessary to ensure the adaptation of the organizational culture with the digital skills that the company acquires.

When the literature on digital transformation is examined; elements such as strategy, leadership, culture and technology seem to be of critical importance. Influencing the success of digital transformation; attention is drawn to a model incorporating strategy and culture (Kane et al., 2015; Schumacher et al., 2016; Canetta et al., 2018; Klein, 2020; Asiltürk, 2021; Oğan & Wolff, 2022). Therefore, it can be said that the digital transformation strategies created within the framework of "Enerjisa Production" cover and support the relevant models.

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